

Campus Recruitment Prediction System using Machine Learning

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Abstract- Placement of students is one of an educational institution's most essential goals. An institution's reputation and annual admissions are inextricably linked to the placements it offers its students. That is why all institutions work tirelessly to grow their placement departments in order to improve the institution as a whole. Any support in this area will improve an institution's capacity to place students. This will always benefit both students and the institution. The goal of this study is to evaluate previous year's student data and utilise it to forecast the placement possibilities of current students. This model is proposed along with an algorithm for predicting the same. Data for the study were acquired from the same institution as the placement prediction, and appropriate data pre-processing methods were used. The proposed approach also informs students about which skill sets to improve and provides insights into various majors of choosing.

Keywords-*Linear Logistic regression, Preprocessing, Prediction.*

I. Introduction

Placements are considered very significant for each and every college. The basic success of the college is determined by the students' campus placements. Every student takes admission to universities based on the proportion of placements. As a result, in this respect, the approaches concerning the prediction and analysis for the placement necessity in the colleges that helps to construct the colleges and students to enhance their placements [1-3].

The Placement Prediction system uses classification algorithms such as Decision Tree and Random Forest to forecast the likelihood of an undergraduate student being placed in a company. The major goal of this model is to forecast whether or not a student will be placed during campus recruitment. The data analysed is the students' academic background, such as overall percentage, backlogs, and credits. The algorithms are applied on the previous years data of the students.

Problem Statement: We present a Placement Prediction System that forecasts the likelihood of an undergrad student being placed in an IT business. We assess the student's academic history, speciality, and skill set, which are tested by hiring firms during the recruitment process.

Purpose: To develop a method for forecasting student placements and providing them with a clear understanding of where they stand in the placement process, as well as suggestions for what else they might do to improve their position.

Scope: This project will assist students by estimating the cutoff based on prior firms and their required skill sets, which were advantageous to the interviewers and the companies they represented. This method will also assist users in increasing their chances of being picked by forecasting the skill set required for their desired job as well as their present skill level.

Objectives: The major goal is to improve the continuing placement prediction system with machine learning techniques. Predict the abilities needed for the desired employment based on their existing specialism.

Methodology: We utilise K-means classification as our basis model to determine the chance of a student being placed. There would be two classes examined for classification: yes and no. Following that, the model's results would be compared to those obtained using logistic regression. The aforementioned features are implemented in Python.

A. EDA

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) is a method for analysing data using visual tools. It is used to find trends, patterns, or to test assumptions using statistical summaries and graphical representations, as well as to examine datasets and summarise their essential properties, frequently using visual methods [4-6].

The Steps in Exploratory Data Analysis In Python are-

1. **Data Description:** Understanding the various types of data and associated statistics is necessary before proceeding to the next steps. A excellent place to start is with the describe() function in Python.
2. **Handling missing data:** Real-world data is not always clean and consistent. Data can be missing during extraction or gathering for a variety of reasons. Missing values must be handled carefully because they degrade the quality of any of our performance matrices.
3. **Handling outliers:** An outlier is something that is distinct from the crowd. Outliers can be the result of a mistake made during data collection or simply a sign of volatility in your data.
4. **Visualisation:** Use Histograms, HeatMaps, and other graphical representations to uncover data relationships.

A. K-means classification

K-means is an unsupervised categorisation technique that divides items into k groups according to their attributes. The grouping is performed by reducing the sum of the distances between each item and the group or clustercentroid.

The classification as per this algorithm is done based on the distances between the training data and the testing data. The distances are calculated using Euclidean Distance. Here k is a positive integer.

Algorithm 1. K-means algorithm.

1. Determine the value of k .
2. Calculate the gap between each training record and the testing record.
3. Sort neighbours by increasing distance.
4. Select the first neighbours from the sorted list.
5. Identify the neighborhood's dominant class and assign it to training data.

B. Euclidean Distance.

The Euclidean distance measures the distance between two places in space. This distance can be used to measure the similarity of two points.

Euclidean distance calculates the square root of the difference in coordinates between two objects.

C: Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is a method for estimating the probability of a discrete outcome based on an input variable. Logistic regression is a useful analysis tool for classification problems, which include determining whether a new sample fits well into a category.

A bilinear interaction (Figure 1) occurs when the slope of a regression line for Y and X changes as a linear function of a third variable, Z .

1. Import packages.
2. Collect Data.
3. Create a model and train it.
4. Evaluate the model.

Figure 1. Logistic Regression

3.Dataset Description

The dataset used is taken from kaggle (Table 2) . It has 14 different attributes and 1028 instances . It does not have any missing values . The features are described in the table given below.

Table 2. Dataset features

<i>S.NO</i>	<i>Attribute</i>	<i>Code given</i>	<i>Data type</i>
1	serial number	sl_no	Numeric
2	Gender	gender	Binary
3	Ssc percentage	Ssc_p	Numeric
4	Ssc board	Ssc_b	Numeric
5	Hsc percentage	Hsc_p	Numeric
6	Hsc board	Hsc_b	Nominal
7	Hsc stream	Hsc_s	Nominal
8	Degree percentage	Degree_p	Numeric
9	Degree type	Degree_t	Nominal
10	Internship experience	Intern_ex	Binary
11	Exam test percentage	etest_p	Numeric
12	specialisation	specialisation	Nominal
13	MBA percentage	mba_p	Numeric
14	Status	Status	Binary

The dataset is visualised to urge the number of placement status of the students and number of placed students and not placed students data within males and female students each.

Figure 2. Results of data visualization

4. Testing and Results

The proposed algorithms are implemented in Python using libraries such as pandas, matplotlib, and sklearn, with the tensorflow library being imported for neural networks. The dataset was downloaded from Kaggle. Machine learning techniques such as linear regression and K-means were employed. The results show that Logistic Regression achieves 57.89 accuracy, while K-means yields nearly the same accuracy as the Logistic Regression model, which is 48.24%, and K Nearest Neighbour achieves 9.9% less than Logistic Regression and Random Forest. Logistic Regression achieved the lowest accuracy rate among all other algorithms, 48.24%.

5. Conclusion

Every university conducts placement analysis, which is important to students looking for work after completing their academic work. In this investigation, two classification methods, EDA and logistic regression (bilinear), and a clustering technique, K-means, were used. The performance of various classification and clustering methods is compared based on the time required to forecast classes. The promising contribution of ML classifiers is observed.

References

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